

Analysis of Electroencephalography Signals for Sentiment Classification: An Integrated Machine Learning and Deep Learning Approach

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Abstract - Sentiment detection is an expanding area aimed at comprehending human emotions from various data sources, including text, voice, and physiological signals such as Electroencephalography (EEG). EEG, a non-invasive technique monitoring brain activity, has gained prominence in this pursuit, employed in both clinical and research contexts to investigate brain responses to emotions. This approach becomes particularly valuable in limited communication scenarios, such as brain-computer interfaces and mental health. For this purpose, machine learning and deep learning are essential. Models such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Deep Neural Networks (DNN), and Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (GCNN) have achieved success in sentiment classification. In this study, these models were explored and compared for emotion detection from EEG. The DNN model achieved a remarkable accuracy of 86.08%, outperforming SVM, albeit with significant processing time. The GCNN model, with its non-linear learning approach, achieved an average accuracy of 87.04% in the experiment, emerging as the most promising methodology for future research.

Keywords: Sentiment detection; Emotion recognition; Electroencephalography (EEG); Deep learning; Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (GCNN).

INTRODUCTION

The detection and understanding of human emotions play a crucial role in advancing interactions between humans and technological systems. In recent years, signal processing, machine learning, and artificial intelligence techniques have shown promise in analyzing Electroencephalography (EEG) signals for sentiment classification (1). EEG, which records brain activity, provides data and insights into emotional states, revealing neural responses to emotional stimuli (2).

Human emotion recognition spans various modalities, including audiovisual expressions, body language, and physiological signals. Among these, physiological signals such as EEG, ECG, and EMG stand out due to their difficulty to conceal. EEG has garnered increasing attention due to the development of accessible and non-invasive devices, enabling applications in emotional recognition in research and clinical settings.

The significance of this research is evident in its applicability in mental health, brain-computer interfaces, and human behavior analysis. The analysis of EEG signals for sentiment detection can enhance clinical diagnostics, personalize therapies, and facilitate more natural interactions between humans and technology.

Despite many efforts to explore machine learning models like SVM, DNN, and DGCNN on EEG signals, challenges persist due to overlapping patterns of brain activation, inter-individual variability, and noise in EEG signals (3).

The current research aims to advance emotion detection in EEG by evaluating models such as SVM, DNN, and DGCNN, contributing to a comprehensive analysis of machine learning approaches in this multidisciplinary and innovative context.

DEVELOPMENT

The evolution of computational neuroscience and machine learning enables the advancement of emotion recognition techniques from Electroencephalography (EEG)

data. The integration of deep learning approaches, such as Graph Convolutional Neural Networks, can enhance the ability to identify complex patterns in EEG signals (3).

In this study, the publicly available SJTU Emotion EEG Dataset (SEED) (4), was employed, acquired non-invasively through electrodes placed on the scalps of participants exposed to auditory and visual stimuli in the form of clips from Chinese emotional films. EEG data were collected from 15 individuals (7 males and 8 females, mean age = 23.27) who underwent three chronologically disconnected sessions.

The SJTU Emotion EEG Dataset (SEED) provides intrinsic features of EEG signals that can be explored for the analysis of relevant patterns in identifying participants' emotions (5). These features include Differential Entropy (DE), Power Spectral Density (PSD), Differential Asymmetry (DASM), Rational Asymmetry (RASM), Asymmetry (ASM), and Differential Causality (DCAU). The data distribution for each attribute/session in the dataset is presented in Fig. 1.

For the classification task, three distinct models were employed: Support Vector Machines (SVM) (4), Deep Neural Networks (DNN) (2) and Dynamic Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNN) (6), exploring their capabilities in analyzing emotional brain responses.

Feature	Number of EEG Features per sample				
	δ	θ	α	β	γ
PSD	62	62	62	62	62
DE	62	62	62	62	62
DASM	27	27	27	27	27
RASM	27	27	27	27	27
ASM	54	54	54	54	54
DCAU	23	23	23	23	23

Figure 1. Description of SEED Dataset Attributes

Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a machine learning technique that aims to find the separation hyperplane that maximizes the margin between data classes in a feature space (4). This is achieved by identifying the hyperplane that maximizes the distance between it and the closest points of each class, known as support vectors, allowing effective generalization to new data (3).

In the context of emotion recognition from EEG data, SVM is applied by transforming brain activity patterns into a feature space and training it to find the optimal hyperplane for separating different emotions. For this study, a linear kernel was adopted, and the parameter C was defined through a grid search over the sets $[2^{(-10)}, 2^{(-9)}, \dots, 2^{10}]$ and $[0.1, 20]$, with a step size of 0.5 for large and small steps, respectively.

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)

Deep learning, based on Artificial Neural Networks, has revolutionized various fields with its ability to learn complex representations directly from raw data (7). Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), with multiple hidden layers, can automatically extract relevant features from EEG signals, enabling more precise and robust classifications of emotions, which are essential for advancements in understanding emotional brain responses (8).

For the DNN model used in this study, there are three hidden layers with 128, 64, and 32 hidden units. The output layer has three units corresponding to three emotions (positive, negative, and neutral). The nonlinear activation functions used are ReLU. The optimization algorithm employed was RMSProp, and the number of epochs was set to 5,000.

Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (GCNN)

The GCNN architecture utilizes graph-adapted convolution operations, allowing each node in the graph to interact with its neighbors, thus capturing contextual and relational information. This makes GCNN particularly suitable for pattern recognition in complex relational data (9). When dealing with data in such contexts, the GCNN architecture preserves the advantages of DNNs, such as the ability to learn hierarchical and abstract representations, while incorporating the structure and specific connections of the given data (10).

For the GCNN model, the input layer corresponds to EEG features extracted from multiple frequency bands. After the graph filtering operation, there is a 1×1 convolution layer, aimed at learning discriminative features among various frequency domains. Additionally, to achieve the network's non-linear mapping capability, the ReLU activation function is adopted to ensure that the outputs of the graph filtering layer are non-negative. Finally, the outputs of the activation function are passed to a multi-layer fully connected network, and a softmax function is also used to predict the desired class label information from the input EEG features. The architecture of the GCNN Network used in this work is presented in Fig. 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results presented in Table 1 and Fig. 3 demonstrate that the Differential Entropy (DE) features exhibited higher accuracy and lower standard deviation than the

Figure 2. Architecture *GCNN*

traditional Power Spectral Density (PSD) features. This suggests that DE features are more suitable for EEG-based emotion recognition than other features. Another important conclusion is that the asymmetry features (DASM, RASM, ASM) performed similarly, and in some cases better than PSD, despite having fewer dimensions (135 (27 pairs of electrodes \times 5 bands), 135 (27 pairs of electrodes \times 5 bands), 270 (54 pairs of electrodes \times 5 bands), and 310 (62 electrodes \times 5 bands), respectively). This suggests that emotion-related brain processing for positive, neutral, and negative emotions exhibits asymmetric characteristics.

Table 1. Resultados dos modelos descritos por Atributo.

Model	Feature	All Frequencies
<i>SVM</i>	DE	84.44/11.58
	PSD	77.99/13.91
	DASM	76.88/14.46
	RASM	76.8/14.44
	ASM	76.45/14.37
	DCAU	81.43/11.62
<i>DNN</i>	DE	86.08/8.34
	PSD	61.90/16.65
	DASM	72.73/15.93
	RASM	71.30/16.16
	ASM	70.76/15.27
	DCAU	77.20/14.24
<i>GCNN</i>	DE	87.04/8.49
	PSD	81.73/9.94
	DASM	78.45/11.84
	RASM	85.00/12.47
	ASM	79.41/11.57
	DCAU	81.91/10.06

Source: Authored by the Author.

These results suggest that features such as DE and asymmetry may be more relevant for emotion detection in EEG signals than traditional features like PSD. Furthermore, the use of smoothing algorithms and the selection of the right classifier can have a significant impact on emotion recognition accuracy.

Figure 3. Results (Accuracy/Standard Deviation) of all the models described.

The DNN classifier outperformed the SVM classifier, achieving an emotion recognition accuracy of 86.08%.

For the GCNN model, the experimental results presented in Table 1 demonstrate that the proposed method achieves better recognition performance than previous methods. The average recognition accuracy reached 87.04% for the subject-dependent experiment due to the following key points:

- The use of a non-linear neural network in GCNN makes it more effective in handling nonlinear discriminative feature learning.
- The graph-based representation of GCNN provides a useful way to characterize the intrinsic relationships between different EEG channels, advantageous for extracting the most discriminative features for emotion recognition.
- The GCNN model adaptively learns the intrinsic relationships of EEG channels by optimizing the adjacency matrix W .

CONCLUSION

By applying machine learning techniques to the analysis of EEG signals and human emotions, we enhance the understanding of the connections between brain activity and emotional states. The results obtained in the study indicate that Deep Neural Networks are viable for sentiment analysis in EEG, with the potential to improve sentiment classification and, therefore, their respective applications, such as mental health and brain-computer interaction.

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